

Beyond economics: Covid-19 vaccination and religious motivations in Romania's 2025 presidential elections

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Abstract

This article investigates the factors shaping voter preferences in Romania's 2025 presidential election, focusing on the runoff between a centrist and a nationalist-conservative-populist candidate. Using electoral data combined with regional indicators, the analysis assesses the relative importance of economic development and Covid-19 vaccination rates – considered a proxy for cultural contextual landscapes related to historical legacies, religiosity and traditionalism. As expected, economic and social development are associated with greater support for the centrist candidate. However, cultural factors also play a decisive role: Covid-19 vaccination rates at the county level, followed by support for traditionalism measured by attitude towards the 2019 “Family” Referendum, are both strong predictors of support for the conservative candidate. These findings highlight the persistence of cultural and attitudinal divides in shaping political preferences in post-communist Romania, and the need to account for them alongside socioeconomic explanations.

Keywords

Electoral behavior; populism; religion; Covid-19 vaccination; post-communist Romania

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Introduction

Across advanced and emerging democracies, far-right populism has shifted from sporadic episodes to a durable presence in electoral politics. Explanations for this rise diverge. One line of work emphasizes economic insecurity and dislocation, from trade shocks and deindustrialization to wage stagnation and perceived status loss (Algan et al, 2017; Colantone and Stanig, 2018; Kurer, 2020). A second direction stresses cultural dynamics, arguing that value change, identity threat, and disputes over moral order, rather than pocket-book concerns, drive its support (Margalit et al., 2025; Norris and Inglehart 2019). At the same time, economic and cultural drivers of populism do not operate in isolation from one another (Gidron and Hall, 2017). Furthermore, the demand-side accounts of populism (centered on economic or cultural grievances) are complemented by explanations focused on those on the supply-side, whereby populist actors' rise is prompted by citizens' disenchantment with unresponsive institutions (Berman, 2021).

Recent culturalist accounts place the post-pandemic information environment center-stage. Under Covid-19, conspiracy narratives and anti-expert discourses flourished, creating favorable conditions for populist entrepreneurs. Work on "medical populism" shows how leaders fuse anti-elitism, people-centrism, and crisis theatrics to politicize disease management and recast experts and bureaucrats as self-serving (see Lasco and Curato, 2019). Parallel research links epistemic distrust to rule-breaking, lower compliance, and vaccine hesitancy (Čavojová et al., 2024; Sturgis et al., 2021). While causal sequencing remains debated, a consistent empirical pattern ties skepticism toward institutions of knowledge to subsequent receptivity to anti-system appeals. In short, Covid-era health behaviors can serve as tractable, behavioral proxies for deeper cultural orientations toward authority, science, and collective obligation, that are central to contemporary populist alignments.

Romania's 2025 presidential elections provide a strong test for these claims. On the one hand, the country has experienced substantial material convergence over the past decade, with rising GDP per capita and downward trends in inequality and poverty (Eurostat 2025a; Eurostat 2025b). On the other hand, the 2018 "Family" referendum, though invalid due to low turnout, helped normalize a triad in public debate: Orthodox religiosity, Romanian ethnonational identity, and a heteronormative family ideal (Norocel and Băluță, 2023). Subsequent analyses show how the narrative of forced vaccination has been embraced by the conservative movement, along with its strong emphasis on patriarchal discourse and proximity to religion (Băluță and Tufiş, 2024). Moreover, during the Covid-19 period, Romania registered one of the highest excess-mortality rates globally, despite relatively early access to vaccines via EU procurement, underscoring the importance of compliance, trust in expertise, and (dis)information by religious networks that shape health behavior (The Economist 2025). Taken together, these developments suggest a cultural infrastructure primed to translate pandemic-era epistemic rifts into electoral cleavages.

The 2024-2025 electoral cycle sharpened this tension. The annulment of the 2024 presidential first round on foreign-interference grounds, the brief surge of Călin Georgescu, a newcomer blending conspiracist and salvationist themes, and the 2025 runoff strength of George Simion (AUR) all point to high demand for anti-establishment appeals despite macroeconomic gains. At the same time, distinct features of the Romanian context, diaspora mobilization, a Hungarian-minority backlash against ethnonationalist cues, and the long tail of pandemic controversies, create within-country variation useful for adjudicating competing explanations. If economic conditions were primary, development indicators should dominate county-level voting patterns; if cultural-epistemic factors matter more, pandemic health-behavior markers should retain predictive power when development is held constant.

This article leverages that opportunity. We test whether county-level Covid-19 vaccination uptake in 2021, a behavioral proxy for trust in expertise, and also for ties to religio-moral networks, predicts support for the anti-establishment candidate (George Simion) in the 2025 presidential runoff, net of development and other covariates.

Empirically, we estimate structural equation models (SEM) at the county level to recover direct and mediated paths among development, cultural proxies (2018 referendum turnout, 2021 vaccination rate), ethnolinguistic composition, and the 2025 vote. Anticipating our results, vaccination in 2021 emerges as the strongest predictor of Simion's county performance, while economic variables have a limited, largely mediated role. We complement this with evidence from school-level data in Cluj-Napoca, where vaccination rates among teachers are substantially lower in religious schools than in comparable non-religious schools, despite similar socio-economic contexts—reinforcing the interpretation of vaccination as a proxy for exposure to religious networks and associated norms.

The structure of the article follows the rationale behind our argument. First, we review existing literature about economic and cultural explanations for support of populism. Second, we explore the connection between Covid-19 hesitancy and its instrumentalization by populist actors. Third, we succinctly describe the political and social context of the Covid-19 pandemic and vaccination in Romania. Fourth, we provide an overview of 2024/2025 Romanian elections. Fifth, we analyze county-level data regarding determinants of populist vote in the most recent presidential elections, singling out vaccination rate as its main predictor.

Economic and cultural explanations of support for populist political actors

A common division in the discussion of populism's appeal is that between economic and cultural explanations (Margalit et al., 2025; Rodrik, 2021). The two perspectives emphasize different underlying processes, and yet a perfect separation of economic and cultural elements is somewhat problematic at theoretical level (Brils et al., 2022; Rodrick, 2021), especially since empirical research often finds that a blend of economic and cultural factors motivate the populist vote (Rhodes-Purdy et al., 2021).

Support for populist actors is postulated by economic approaches as rooted in economic dissatisfaction and material loss or insecurities (Rhodes-Purdy et al., 2021). Let down by worsening economic conditions, citizens become responsive to populists' agendas, because the latter seem to offer convincing solutions to difficult economic circumstances (Margalit, 2019). The literature refers to a variety of processes that may result in deteriorating economic conditions likely to generate discontent: disruptions in the labor markets prompted by globalization (Colantone and Stanig, 2018), deindustrialization that pitches some regions into a state of economic relapse (Guriev and Papaioannou, 2022), the rise of unemployment associated to economic crises (Algan et al., 2017), austerity resulting from government reforms (Fetzer, 2019).

Margalit (2019) is rather reserved about the explanatory strength of economic insecurity for understanding the endorsement of populist actors, questioning the extent to which they stand for its core causes. Indeed, the empirical tests of economic explanations produce mixed results. For example, referring to Poland, Olejnik and Wroński (2025) argue that economic factors provide a solid explanation of the success of the Law and Justice party in the 2019 elections. Their analyses show that votes from economically disadvantaged areas had an important bearing in the populist party's electoral achievement, thus stressing the impact of "uneven economic development" (Olejnik and Wroński, 2025: 686). Conversely, Brils, Muis and Gaidytė (2022) find little support for socioeconomic deprivation being a convincing predictor of vote for far-right parties. Comparing far right voters with supporters of center-right parties, of left parties and with non-voters from 17 European countries, the

authors show that supporters of the far-right are economically worse off only if compared to those who endorse -center-right parties. Furthermore, in the new democracies from the so-called Eastern bloc, unemployment is unrelated to far-right preference. Notably, Brils and colleagues (2022) call for caution in assuming synonymy between far-right parties and populist parties.

Tapping into the economic underpinnings of populist appeal seems somewhat more straightforward than specifying the cultural mechanisms behind it. Margalit, Raviv and Solodoch (2025) sought to bring some order in the diverse (and often intertwined) cultural arguments and located five culture-focused “storylines” in the extant scholarship. These different accounts emphasize respectively: the tension caused by value change, whereby traditional values lose their primacy; concerns over the dilution of national identity resulting from growing migration; frustration over the neglect of rural areas, in contrast with the rising affluence of urban regions; worries about the deterioration of social status among formerly privileged groups; declining cohesion of communities, driven by urbanization and industrialization (Margalit et al., 2025). An important comment about these different cultural explanations is that they all involve, albeit to a varying degree, economic catalysts, underscoring the difficulty to wholly separate analytically the two types of factors. Furthermore, the empirical test on the five scenarios on European Social Survey data confirms the assortment of cultural and economic distress among voters for right wing populist parties, while also revealing that many of these voters do not manifest economic anxieties (Margalit et al., 2025).

Among the cultural approaches to populism, Norris and Inglehart’s (2019) cultural backlash theory is likely the most renowned. Their explanation is centered on the cultural shifts in Western societies, a change fueled by “generational replacement, rising educational levels, growing ethnic diversity, gender equality, and urban growth” (Norris and Inglehart, 2019: 42). These dynamics create a context where notable parts of the population feel uneasy in a society perceived as no longer aligned to their values, identities and customs. On top of this new state of things, where comparatively more support for progressive values make social conservatives feel estranged, added insecurities stemming from economic difficulties and mounting immigration stir the “authoritarian reflexes” involved in the electoral support for authoritarian-populist leaders (Norris and Inglehart, 2019: 33-35). Although material concerns play a non-marginal part in the overall explanation, the authors underline the resentment of changing cultural norms, turning the values-driven backlash into the main mechanism for understanding the ascent of populism.

Though remarkably influential, the cultural backlash thesis is not immune to criticism. Schäfer (2022) argues that its general argument, based on intergenerational change, is weakened by an overstatement of the divergence between younger and older generations. After replicating the original analysis, Schäfer finds that “the data do not support the claim that in European societies, younger and older cohorts stand on two sides of a cultural conflict in which the old defend authoritarian, and the young libertarian values” (Schäfer, 2022: 1983). The author also takes issue with Norris and Inglehart’s interpretation of consecutive generations’ electoral preferences for authoritarian and populist parties, claiming that, in fact, the vote for authoritarian-populist parties is more likely for the younger cohorts. Although cautious on the ability of the cultural backlash theory to unambiguously account for populists’ success, Schäfer (2022) recognizes the valence of cultural interpretations and confirms that opposition to immigration is an essential factor in explaining preference for authoritarian-populist parties.

Recently, the cultural backlash theory was appraised by Baro and Jenssen (2025), who argue that the approach works better at explaining the rise of populism in the US rather than in Europe. As the latter accommodates a diversity of national contexts with quite specific historical journeys, making it unlikely for cultural change to have occurred at the same pace everywhere, different drivers of

populism might be at work in different countries. Their analyses of Hungary, Italy, Poland, and Norway indeed point in this direction. For instance, social conservative values and religion are stronger predictors of vote for populist parties in Poland than in Hungary, where these factors fail to explain the phenomenon, yet where nationalism stands out as the driving force of the populist preference. At the same time, in both countries, holding authoritarian values has higher effect on the populist vote than in the remaining cases, a process interpreted by the authors as stemming from their recent undemocratic past (Baro and Jenssen, 2025).

Anti-vaccination attitudes and the populist appeal during the pandemic

The developments generated by the outbreak of the Covid pandemic set the stage for a value-driven “rebellion” of those who felt betrayed by the elites’ and experts’ insistent appeals at risk-minimizing behaviors. Conspiracy theories flourished against the context created by the health crisis, producing an auspicious environment for populist political actors (Oana and Bojar, 2023). Castanho-Silva, Vegetti and Littvay (2017: 437) clarify how “the tendency to adopt a Manichean outlook to social events, and more importantly, the underlying narrative that sees anything official as deceptive” create the proximity between conspiracy thinking and populist perspectives.

Attitudes towards vaccination during the Covid-19 pandemic need to be understood within a broader context of anti-vaccination trends in general, which, in turn are deeply embedded in psychology. While Hornsey et al. (2018) speak about a process of motivated reasoning – through which pre-existing views of the world are reinforced by seeking out information consistent with them (although they may be false), Imhoff and Lamberty (2020) consider that conspiracies bring an illusory sense of control in the context of the Covid-19 pandemic. In a study on US and UK data, they show that conspiracies affect behavior in the context of the pandemic, but that different types of conspiracies trigger different behavioral reactions (so not all conspiracy believers act similarly in the face of restrictions). For example, those believing that the pandemic is a hoax were against behavior limiting restrictions, while those who believed it to be man-made were not (Imhoff and Lamberty, 2020). In a 2022 study of German general public and experts, Rothmund et al. explore the performance of three psychology-derived factors in explaining pandemic denial: “(a) cognitive capacity and style, (b) political identity and alignment, and (c) exposure to misinformation in social media” (Rothmund et al., 2022: 440-441). Results show two groups that are significantly prone to deny the existence of the pandemic, the dismissive and the doubtful: “both groups express higher levels of collective narcissism and are more likely to report a rightwing political ideology” (Rothmund et al., 2022: 451). The pandemic is thus perceived as a threat to political identity, as the dismissive show increased distrust towards scientists and politicians alike, and also increased anti-elitism.

A notable part of the controversies during the pandemic revolved around vaccination, turning vaccine hesitancy into a salient occurrence (Troiano and Nardi, 2021). In a study on 24 nations and Hong Kong, anti-vaccination attitudes have been shown previously to be linked to conspiracy beliefs, to reactance, to disgust vis-à-vis needles/blood, and a worldview emphasizing individualism (Hornsey et al., 2018). Reactance refers to people’s tendency to get attached to views opposed to opinions endorsed by the majority and stems from the desire to be or to be perceived as autonomous and uncompliant (Hornsey et al., 2018). Moreover, anti-vaccination attitudes are also correlated with conservative political ideologies (Hornsey et al., 2018). In a 30 nations study, (Tybur et al., 2016) found that antipathogen strategies are clearly associated with conservatism, but more so to upholding traditions and norms (as cultural and evolutionary survival mechanism against disease) than to opposing ethnically/racially different groups.

Even before the pandemic, Baumgaertner et al. (2018) showed, on a study on US data, that ideology influences intention to vaccinate, with conservatives being less prone to vaccinate. As it turns out, ideology affects intention to vaccinate indirectly as well, through measures of trust in medical expertise, conservatives being more numerous in this group, suggesting a type of motivated reasoning. In 2019, Featherstone et al. found that liberal ideology is at odds with acceptance of vaccine conspiracies. Moreover, Christian nationalism in the US was also found to be positively correlated with vaccine hesitancy (Corcoran et al. 2021). Although many studies on the effect of ideology were conducted in the US, research findings from European countries find similar, albeit weaker results. For example, on Italian data, Cadeddu et al. (2020) found that anti-vaccine attitudes correlate with identification with ideologies on the right end of the spectrum, as well as less participation in political or cultural matters (also male, older, less educated). Alternatively, Czarnek et al. (2020) found that rightwing ideology is negatively associated with pro-vaccine attitude (on 2019 Eurobarometer data) only in the subset of politically interested respondents. In the former communist part of Europe, there seems to be at least partial overlap between right-wing populism and anti-vaccine attitudes structured along the anti (medical) elitist argument, as Žuk and Žuk (2020) show on a study of discourses on YouTube video clips in Polish language. In an effort to distinguish between two dimensions of authoritarianism (RWA – right wing authoritarianism focusing on social control, and SDO – social dominance orientation focusing on inequality as natural), Bielewicz and Soral (2021) found, on German, Polish and British data, that RWA was associated with less vaccine hesitancy, while SDO with more. Furthermore, another study on 2019 Eurobarometer data shows that vaccine reluctance is associated with ideological extremism, as opposed to just right-wing extremism (Debus and Tosun 2021).

As already suggested by the previous observations, the anti-elite sentiment that permeates the populist system of beliefs (see Mudde, 2004) is a key element that sustains the link between anti-vaccination stances and populist attitudes. The literature seems to concur on this aspect, whether referring to vaccination in general or to vaccination during the Covid pandemic (Kennedy, 2019; Stoeckel et al., 2022). Notably, the aversion towards elites is not limited to political leaders, but extends to scientists and experts, resulting in contestation and distrust on the part of citizens (Stoeckel et al., 2022; Mede and Schäfer, 2020). Conservative political actors play an important part in the heated debates over vaccination, fueling the perceived divide between people and elites. Such a process is expressively labelled by Lasco and Curato (2019: 1) as “medical populism”, meaning “a political style that constructs antagonistic relations between ‘the people’ whose lives have been put at risk by ‘the establishment.’” Along with insisting on the fracture between the citizens and the establishment, medical populism is likely to involve the plain rejection of scientific expertise (Lasco and Curato, 2019). According to Lasco (2020), during the pandemic, political leaders like Bolsonaro, Duterte and Trump repeatedly played down the risks posed by the virus and bluntly capitalized on the anti-science sentiment in order to build support.

Different levels of stringency of containment measures throughout the Covid-19 pandemic suggest that, at least at the beginning, there was little information about effectiveness of policies in reducing incidence of cases. Consequently, and because of a lack of a precedent that governments could rely on, politics did not seem to influence policy in 26 European democracies, during the first wave of the pandemic (Plümper and Neumeyer, 2022). Nevertheless, subsequent waves saw a return of politics because of both policy learning (increased availability of policy effectiveness) and a waning of public support for the incumbent government initially existing (Plümper and Neumeyer, 2022).

In Romania, more specifically, Pop-Eleches (2025) explores the potential explanations of the electoral success of populist radical right (PRR) parties, with a focus on the parliamentary elections

from 2024. The author shows that, among the retrospective voting drivers, Covid-related factors (level of satisfaction with how the state managed the pandemic and having/having not been administered the vaccine) had greater influence on the support of PRR parties than citizens' views on economic aspects. Importantly, a similar finding also emerged in relation to the vote for the two populist candidates in the presidential elections, Georgescu and Simion, which suggest that the pandemic period continues to be salient and consequential for citizens' electoral choices (Pop-Eleches, 2025).

Other sources point to religious factors influencing vaccine hesitancy. For example, Martens and Rutjens (2022) find that religiosity and spirituality are associated with lower anti Covid-19 vaccination rates in different regions of the world, even when controlling for vaccine supply issues. Moreover, religiosity negatively correlates with vaccination even when GDP, age, collectivism, vaccine skepticism, and record of previous inoculations (Martens and Rutjens, 2022) are accounted for. Similarly, on Australian longitudinal data, Edwards et al. (2021) found that higher religiosity and populist views were negatively associated with the intention to vaccinate, while income and trust in authorities (and hospitals) were positively associated with it. In an experimental study on US data, Chu et al. (2021) found that the decision to vaccinate was influenced by medical experts conveying a common religious identity message to the public as well as making clear references to religion. In an encompassing review of 20 studies on vaccine hesitancy and its potential religious roots in different areas of the world, Imran et al. (2024) argue that, in general, higher religiosity is associated with vaccine hesitancy, a relationship often mediated by mistrust in science and the scientific community. Given that the Covid-19 pandemic created a surge in people's need for religion (Sinding Bentzen, 2021), as a source of solace and response in the face of adversity, it is conceivable that, in certain contexts, religiosity did contribute to vaccine hesitancy significantly.

In the context of our study, religious correlates of vaccine hesitancy are seen as representative of a distinct cultural perspective, exploited by right-wing populists for electoral gain. Conspiracies creating the landscape of vaccine hesitancy belong to a certain cultural outlook, where tradition and identity fuel anti-scientific expert positionings, adopted and instrumentalized by populist actors.

The pandemic in Romania: conspiracy theories and skepticism towards vaccination

In the fourth quarter of 2021, the Covid crisis in Romania became manifestly worrisome, with high numbers of daily new cases, alarming numbers of deaths and a rather low vaccination rate (Euronews and AP, 2021; Deutsche Welle, 2021). This happened in a context where, similar to other countries (Eberl et al., 2021) conspiracy theories, some of which questioned the actual existence of the pandemic, became widespread (Durach and Volintiru, 2021; Lup and Mitrea, 2021). Interestingly, Stoica and Umbres (2021) found a surprising positive association between education and holding conspiracy beliefs. One of the explanations suggested by the authors is that distrust of government in Romania is particularly pronounced among the better educated, making them skeptical about the pandemic-related messages communicated by the official authorities.

Relatedly, the contradictions and ambiguity that hindered the official messages delivered by the Romanian authorities have turned parts of the public wary of the pandemic-related official communication (Cmeci et al., 2022; Džakula et al., 2022). Moreover, like elsewhere in Europe, the restriction measures issued by the authorities produced substantial discontent, voiced through street protests (Neumeyer et al., 2024). More than a few of these protests have been organized with the support of the populist right-wing party The Alliance for the Union of Romanians, AUR (Doiciar and Cretan, 2021).

Indeed, AUR seems a fitting illustration of a political actor actively engaged in medical populism. The party, led by George Simion, has been particularly vocal in contesting the various restrictions introduced by the authorities, through the organization of multiple protests and an intense online presence which promoted conspiracy narratives around the virus and the vaccines (Burean and Pálffy, 2024). For instance, during 2021, the protests organized by AUR featured banners with telling messages like “Down with the mask!” (as well as the more piercing variant “Down with the mask, we are not dogs!”), “Down with the restrictions!” (Hotnews, 2021), “Down with the medical dictatorship!” (Pricop, 2021), “I believe in God, not in Covid” (Valica, 2021). References to religion were not limited to slogans displayed on banners, as protesters often joined the demonstrations carrying icons or other religious imagery (Benea, 2021; Pricop, 2021).

AUR’s preoccupation with the pandemic (and thereby with the topic of vaccination) endured past the termination of the health crisis: in the summer of 2025, a no-confidence vote against the European Commission has been initiated by a group of MEPs led by a member of AUR (Euractiv, 2025). The motion, ultimately not passed by the European Parliament, was mainly concerned with the handling of the Covid period, specifically with the procurement of vaccines (European Parliament, 2025).

Additionally, throughout the pandemic, religious actors also expressed their view of either restrictions or vaccination repeatedly. However, although the Romanian Orthodox Church is a fairly hierarchical structure, messages diverged. For example, in early 2021 the Romanian Orthodox Church announced that it will get involved in the vaccination campaign, by distributing to their churches a brochure entitled “Covid-19 vaccination in Romania. Free. Voluntary. Safe.” Several high-ranking members of the church expressed pro-vaccination attitudes, such as Archbishop Calinic or Metropolitan Irineu, while the Catholic priest Francisc Doboş was also a supporter of the vaccine (Europa Liberă România, 2021). Although the Romanian Ministry of Health officially announced this information campaign by the Orthodox Church, further statements from the church’s spokesperson stressed that the church cannot guarantee the safety of the Covid-19 vaccine, since it is a purely medical issue, and Fati (2021) considers that such caution may limit the impact of this initiative. One of the most vocal critics of both Covid-19 related restrictions and vaccination is Archbishop Teodosie of Tomis, who called people to mass even when such events were forbidden, and who oscillated from blatantly opposing vaccination based on conspiracy theories (suggesting that those who got vaccinated ended up dying, while the others did not – TVRInfo, 2021), to feigning indifference, but transmitting an anti-vaccination message, and not getting vaccinated himself because of an “allergy”: “we are not saying yes and we are not saying no [about vaccination] [...] Praying cures better than the vaccine [...] The holy sacrament fights any virus. This is why we do not accept administering the holy sacrament with several spoons, this would be blasphemous” (Popescu, 2021).

The 2025 presidential race in context

Romania’s 2025 presidential election followed an exceptional institutional shock. On December 6, 2024, the Constitutional Court annulled the presidential vote after the first round, citing serious irregularities and malign foreign interference, just as diaspora voting was already under way (IFES, 2024). The trigger was the surprise first-place result of Călin Georgescu (22.94%), a political newcomer who campaigned almost exclusively on social media with a discourse mixing conspiracy, mysticism, protochronist nationalism, and anti-Western signaling. Romanian security services tied the information environment to Russian manipulation on TikTok. The Court barred Georgescu from the rerun scheduled for 2025.

The annulment landed in (and contributed to) a context of rising populism. In the June 2024 European Parliament election, the governing PSD–PNL (Social Democratic Party – PSD, National Liberal Party – PNL) alliance finished first, but AUR (Alliance for the Union of Romanians – AUR, right-wing populist) consolidated a strong second (European Parliament, 2024). In the December 1, 2024 parliamentary election, three right-wing populist parties, AUR, POT (Young People Party), and SOS, together exceeded 32% of the vote; AUR alone took 18.3% (its best result yet). Mainstream parties PSD and PNL underperformed at 22.3% and 14.28%, respectively, while USR (Save Romania Union) took 12.26% and UDMR (The Democratic Union of Hungarians in Romania) 6.38% (AEP, 2025). A PSD–PNL–UDMR government under PSD’s Marcel Ciolacu followed. These outcomes signaled broad dissatisfaction with mainstream parties and a clear right-populist surge (Deloy, 2024).

The 2025 presidential rerun crystallized around George Simion (AUR) and Nicușor Dan (independent, pro-EU). In the May 4 first round, with a turnout of just over 53%, Simion led with 40.96%, followed by Dan (20.99%) and Crin Antonescu (PNL, 20.07%). The May 18 runoff, with an increased turnout of nearly 65%, delivered Dan a 53.6–46.4% victory after a rapid consolidation of centrist and liberal voters (Reuters, 2025a; Politico, 2025). International coverage framed the outcome as both a victory of pro-democracy forces in Romania and a reassurance for the pro-Ukrainian strategy of the EU (Henley/The Guardian 2025).

The diaspora played an unusual role. Turnout abroad jumped from about 973,000 votes in the first round to about 1.65 million in the second. Substantively, the diaspora tilted right-populist across cycles: Georgescu took a little over 43% of diaspora ballots in November 2024, and in 2025 Simion won 60.79% of the diaspora in round one and 55.78% in the runoff, even as Dan gained sharply at home (AEP, 2025). This divergence - diaspora leaning more anti-establishment than the domestic electorate - helped shape inter-round strategies.

The ethnic-Hungarian vote was pivotal and moved decisively against Simion. Hungarian-majority counties (Harghita, Covasna) delivered landslides for Dan. Beyond programmatic preferences (EU anchoring, minority-rights guarantees), analysts pointed to Simion’s prior anti-Hungarian activism, notably the 2019 Valea Uzului (Úzvölgye) cemetery confrontation, and antagonistic rhetoric toward the UDMR in 2024. In short, cross-border cues associated with Viktor Orbán did not override local identity concerns; past conflicts and messaging made Simion non-viable for many Hungarian voters (Barberá, 2019; Scheffer, 2025).

The campaign also unfolded amid transatlantic contention. At the February 2025 Munich Security Conference, U.S. Vice-President J. D. Vance publicly questioned the Romanian presidential election annulment. Romanian opposition figures amplified the criticism, while government actors and many analysts rebutted it by invoking the evidentiary basis for the Court’s decision (Henley, 2025). Washington later calibrated its tone, but the episode showed how great-power narratives fed into domestic framing.

Economically, expectations of lower anti-system demand rested on Romania’s rapid convergence: GDP per capita (PPS) reached about 80% of the EU average in 2023/2024; inequality eased as the Gini declined from 37.4 (2015) to 28.0 (2025), below the EU average of 29.4; and the AROPE rate fell from 37.3% (2015) to 27.9% (2024) (European Commission, 2025; Eurostat, 2025a; Eurostat 2025b). The coexistence of these aggregate gains with high anti-establishment votes suggest that additional factors downplayed the potential of economic growth to counter popular dissatisfaction towards the political system.

Beyond material explanations, a culturalist account helps explain the appeal of AUR, based on Georgescu and Simion either complementing or, in places, supplanting economic grievance. The 2018

constitutional “Family” referendum (6-7 October), which failed because of insufficient turnout (21.1%) despite 93.4% support, nonetheless normalized a triad of (Orthodox) religion, Romanian ethnicity, and the heteronormative family as core to national identity and helped pave the way for AUR’s rise (Norocel and Băluță, 2023: 160). In the same arena, anti-feminism and conservative neo-familialism intertwined with religion to sustain a patriarchal “gender contract” and salient homophobic, chauvinistic, and Christian-nationalist attitudes. By 2021, moral-panic narratives about “gender ideology” even began to incorporate forced vaccination (Băluță and Tufiş, 2023: 632). The referendum thus opened a broader discussion about populism and religion.

The apparently direct relationship between religiosity and right-wing populism is, however, more complicated and nuanced. For example, while right-wing populists routinely invoke Christianity, religious communities’ responses vary by national/regional context — many church actors in Germany and France have publicly distanced themselves from AfD or RN, whereas U.S. religious elites have been less inclined to speak against Trump, partly reflecting differences in institutional structure and reach (Cremer, 2023). Conceptually, this landscape supports distinguishing the politicization of religion (Christianity as an identity marker) from the sacralization of politics, where populism and religion share Manichean frames and promises of salvation (Zúquete, 2017). Charismatic leadership can operationalize this overlap through multiple roles — prophet, moral archetype, martyr, leader-as-people, party, and missionary (Zúquete, 2017). Seen through this lens, Georgescu’s brief 2024 surge, amplified by online mobilization and, arguably, later reflected in segments of Simion’s 2025 support, combined prophetic posture, martyr tropes, “leader-as-people” rhetoric, and missionary zeal, offering a form of religious populist re-enchantment amid disenchantment with technocratic governance (Zúquete, 2017).

Data and results

Our unit of analysis is the county (N = 42, including Bucharest). The outcome variable is the county-level share of votes for George Simion in the 2025 presidential runoff from May 18, 2025. The key explanatory variable is the county Covid-19 vaccination rate as measured in late 2021 (according to the official reporting from October 2021). We include in the analysis three contextual covariates, the choice of which is motivated by existing work and the particularities of the Romanian context:

1. Local development: a pre-pandemic Development Index (2017) that captures structural socioeconomic capacity. The index is built by using factor analysis from three variables: GDP/capita; Income; Life expectancy. The resulting index has a high internal consistency, with Cronbach Alpha=0.85.
2. Cultural/traditionalism proxy: measured as turnout in the 2018 “Family” referendum, widely read as a mobilization around Orthodox identity and heteronormative family norms.
3. Ethnolinguistic composition: the percentage of ethnic Hungarians at county level; this variable is included due to the distinctive electoral behavior of Hungarian-majority counties in the elections from 2024–2025.

Figure 1 shows that county-level voting distribution had considerable variation, with support for George Simion reaching 9.1% in Harghita and 58.1% in Călărași. What might explain this variance? Our results indicate that the vote for George Simion is negatively correlated with an Index of Development, positively correlated with turnout in the 2018 “Referendum for Family,” negatively correlated with the COVID-19 vaccination rate in October 2021, and negatively correlated with the percentage of Hungarians (see Table 1). As shown in the table, the percentage of Hungarians in the county has the strongest correlation (negative) with the vote for George Simion ($r = -0.82$), followed by the turnout to the 2018 Family Referendum ($r = 0.57$) and the Development Index ($r = -0.40$).

Figure 1. County-level voting distribution in the second round of the 2025 Romanian presidential elections.

Romania, Presidential Election 2025 — Round 2
George Simion share by county (continuous grayscale)

In this bivariate analysis, the vaccination rate exerts the lowest (yet significant) correlation on the vote for Simion ($r = -0.36$). The Turnout Referendum has the strongest correlation with Vote GS, followed by Index Development and Vaccination Rate. However, when the two counties that have strong majorities of ethnic Hungarians, Covasna and Harghita, are excluded, the strongest predictor of the Vote GS becomes the Vaccination Rate: $r = -0.72^{***}$ (see Figure 2).

Nevertheless, since the chosen explanatory variables are also correlated with one another, further analysis needs to include a multivariate approach to distinguish their individual and mediating effects. The structural equation model we consequently tested is shown in Figure 3.

We built two models: one with all cases ($N=42$), and one where we excluded Covasna (CV) and Harghita (HR), the two counties that have strong majorities of ethnic Hungarians ($N=40$). Both structural equation models exhibit excellent fit, with CFI and TLI $> .95$ and RMSEA $< .03$, surpassing conventional benchmarks (Table 2).

Table 1. Correlations between Vote for George Simion (2025), Development Index (2017), Turnout in the “Family” referendum (2018), Covid-19 Vaccination Rate (October 2021), and % of Hungarians, county level.

		Vote GS 2025	Index Development 2017	Turnout Referendum 2018	Vaccination Rate 2021
Vote GS 2025	r	1.00	-0.40	0.57	-0.36
	p		.009	.000	.018
Index Development 2017	r	-0.40	1.00	-0.41	0.88
	p	.009		.007	.000
Turnout Referendum 2018	r	0.57	-0.41	1.00	-0.43
	p	.000	.007		.004
Vaccination Rate 2021	r	-0.36	0.88	-0.43	1.00
	p	.018	.000	.004	
% Hungarians	r	-0.82	-0.02	-0.51	-0.08
	p	.000	.889	.001	.607

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Figure 2. Correlation between Vaccination Rate (October 2021) and Vote GS (2025) and regression line for all counties except Harghita and Covasna.

Figure 3. Structural equation model for Vote for George Simion (2025), Development Index (2017), Turnout in the “Family” referendum (2018), Covid-19 Vaccination Rate (October 2021), and % of Hungarians, county level.

Table 2. Structural equation estimates for Vote for George Simion (2025), Development Index (2017), Turnout in the “Referendum for Family” (2018), COVID-19 Vaccination Rate (October 2021) at the county level, and percentage of Hungarians (all cases, N=42; all cases except HR and CV, N=40).

			All cases (N=42)			All - HR, CV (N=40)		
			Unstd. coeff.	Std. coeff.	p	Unstd. coeff.	Std. coeff.	p
Vote G Simion	<---	Dev. index	-1.94	-0.17	0.132	-1.14	-0.14	0.449
Vote G Simion	<---	Vaccination rate	-0.53	-0.33	0.006	-0.69	-0.60	0.005
Vote G Simion	<---	% Hungarians	-0.58	-0.90	***	-0.52	-0.52	***
Vote G Simion	<---	Turnout ref.	-0.23	-0.10	0.179	-0.32	-0.17	0.092
Vaccination rate	<---	Turnout ref.	-0.26	-0.18	0.055	-2.09	-0.49	***
Turnout ref.	<---	Dev. index	-2.07	-0.42	***	-0.09	-0.17	0.203
Turnout ref.	<---	% Hungarians	-0.15	-0.51	***	5.34	0.78	***
Vaccination rate	<---	Dev. index	5.59	0.80	***	0.14	0.16	0.008
Vaccination rate	<---	% Hungarians	-0.06	-0.16	0.071	-0.35	-0.22	0.002

The first model indicates that the proportion of Hungarians has the strongest effect on voting for Simion ($\beta = -0.90^{***}$): on average, for each 10% increase in the Hungarian population, Simion lost 6% of the vote. The COVID-19 vaccination rate is the second strongest predictor ($\beta = -0.33^{**}$): each 10% increase in vaccination coverage leads to a 5% decrease in support for Simion. The Development Index does not exhibit a statistically significant direct effect. However, its total effect, mediated through vaccination rates and referendum turnout, is significant (total $\beta = -0.41^{**}$).

The importance of ethnic composition of localities in understanding the populist vote has been previously revealed in the literature. Discussing the growing popularity of AUR in the context created by the pandemic, Armeanu (2025) finds that socio-economic factors are unable to explain the party's electoral achievements at locality level, in the 2020 parliamentary elections. Instead, cultural and political attributes deliver a more convincing account of AUR's political ascent, with electoral support being higher "in localities with low ethnic diversity, low voter turnout and in rural areas" (Armeanu, 2025: 14). In the second model, the effect of the vaccination rate is even stronger ($\beta = -0.60^{**}$): each 10% increase in vaccination coverage leads to a 7% decrease in support for Simion. The total effect of the Development Index, mediated through vaccination rates and referendum turnout, is also stronger (total $\beta = -0.59^{**}$). Bootstrapping, based on 5,000 samples, confirms the statistical significance of the vaccination rate's effect ($p < 0.01$) for both models.

Discussion

The analysis demonstrates that county-level Covid-19 vaccination rates are a robust predictor of support for George Simion in the 2025 presidential election. While vaccination uptake is largely influenced by economic development, over one-third of its variation across counties remains unexplained, suggesting the role of other sociocultural factors.

Religious affiliation and religiosity appear to be particularly relevant. Data collected in November 2021 on school-level vaccination rates among teachers in Cluj-Napoca, Romania's second-largest city, show significant differences across religious affiliations. Among 168 schools (including kindergartens), the overall average vaccination rate was 74%, but among nine schools affiliated with Orthodox, Evangelical, and Pentecostal (OEP) churches, the average dropped to 52%. Of the eight schools with the lowest vaccination rates, six were OEP-affiliated (Inspectoratul Școlar Județean Cluj, 2021). Given the consistency in teacher salaries and shared urban setting, religious networks and norms likely explain this variation.

These results underscore the importance of cultural variables, such as religiosity and moral traditionalism, in shaping political preferences. Indicators like vaccine hesitancy and past participation in the 2018 referendum reflect broader ideological orientations that align with populist, nationalist candidates.

The analysis also highlights the strengths and limitations of contextual-level data. County-level indicators are valuable for capturing broad environmental influences—economic, cultural, and institutional—that are often difficult to measure at the individual level. In this case, contextual data allowed for meaningful comparisons across geographic units in terms of religious conservatism, development, and public health behavior.

However, such data are susceptible to ecological fallacies; correlations observed at the aggregate level may not accurately reflect individual-level relationships. In addition, contextual data obscure within-county variation and limit causal inference. A promising direction for future research is to combine contextual data with individual-level surveys through multilevel modelling. This would allow for a more nuanced understanding of how individual beliefs interact with their social environments to shape electoral behavior.

Conclusions

This study shows that county vaccination uptake (2021) best explains geographic variation in support for George Simion in Romania's 2025 presidential runoff. Economic development matters primarily indirectly, by fostering higher vaccination (and dampening the referendum-style mobilization captured

by 2018 turnout), which in turn is associated with lower support for the anti-establishment candidate. In short, culture-proxied health behavior outperforms material conditions in accounting for the county map of the 2025 vote. Corroborating these results with our finding regarding low vaccine uptake among teachers at religious schools, and the already documented association between religiosity and vaccine hesitancy, we assert that low vaccination rates are indicative of a set of cultural features, among which religiosity ranks high, that explain the vote for the right-wing populist candidate.

Therefore, a key implication of our study is the central role of religiosity and religious-network mobilization in contemporary far-right dynamics. Our findings align with the view that religious institutions, congregational ties, and clergy cues shape the informational and moral environments in which pandemic-era skepticism, and, by extension, anti-establishment politics, can thrive. Counties with denser exposure to religious networks appear more conducive to narratives that depress vaccination and elevate populist voting. For example, Suceava, home to the second-highest number of monasteries in Romania (43), recorded the lowest vaccination rate and tied for second through fifth in Simion's vote share, illustrating the general pattern rather than being an outlier. Importantly, this is not necessarily a claim about individual faith per se, but about the organizational capacity and message diffusion of religious networks as brokers of trust, identity, and collective action.

Substantively, the results direct scholarship to measure religiosity as structure and mobilization dynamics, not only as belief. Future research should incorporate indicators such as parish density per capita, attendance/participation rates, religious school presence, local religious media penetration, and documented clergy interventions during campaigns; where possible, these can be linked to event-time exposures (pilgrimages, feast-day rallies), diaspora parish networks, and online sermon circulation. Such measures would help adjudicate whether religious networks amplify medical-populist frames, neutralize them, or do both under different leadership and institutional constraints. Methodologically, multilevel designs that nest individuals within religious and media ecologies, and SEM to trace indirect paths, are well suited to this agenda.

For policy, the results suggest that trust-building with religious communities, co-produced health communication with respected clergy, and local elite engagement may do more to blunt populist surges than macroeconomic messaging alone—while also recognizing that religious actors can be partners in democratic resilience when mobilized toward pro-social norms.

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